

Mourides (Muridiyya)

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Entry tags: Sufi, African Religion, Religious Group

The Mouride tariqa (brotherhood) is headquartered in Ṭūbā, in north-central Senegal, the site of Amadu Bamba Mbaké's 1890s vision of the angel Gabriel and the location for the brotherhood's Grand Magal, an annual pilgrimage that attracts as many as two million devotees. The brotherhood grew out of the Qādiriyya (Xaadir) tariqa, a Ṣūfī movement to which Bamba was himself an adherent. Three distinctive features mark the Mourides. First, their devotion to their order's founder, Amadu Bamba, mirrors the level of veneration often reserved by Muslims for the Prophet Muhammad. Second, their adherence to the principle of hard works makes them ideally suited for agrarian life in the Senegalese countryside. Third, their commitment to principled Islamic nonviolence, even during decades of resistance to French colonial overlords, has much to do with the emergence of Senegal as a nascent West African democracy in a region often beset by civil wars. Bamba's influence cannot be overstated. Mouride Wolof believe that by serving Bamba's vicegerents they participate in the blessing (baraka) of their founder and find a path to eternal life. A suborder of the Mourides, the Baye Fall, was initiated by a close disciple of Bamba's, Ibrahima Fall, who continued his predecessor's emphasis on the virtue of hard work. Other principles that are important to Mourides include mild asceticism, charity toward the order, filial devotion, Arabic and Islamic education, faith in the Hereafter, communal solidarity, the repetition of God's names (dhikr), and the Grand Magal, an annual pilgrimage to the holy city of Touba.

Date Range: 1853 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Senegal

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Senegal

Senegal

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999), pp. 195-210.
- Source 2: Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971).
- Source 3: David Robinson, "Beyond Resistance and Collaboration: Amadu Bamba and the Murids of Senegal" in *Journal of Religion in Africa* Vol. 21, Fasc. 2 (May, 1991), pp. 149-171.
- Source 1: Kate Kingsbury, "Modern Mouride Marabouts and their Young Disciples in Dakar" in *Anthropologica*, 2018, Vol. 60, No. 2 (2018), pp. 467-479.
- Source 2: Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003), pp. 310-327.

- Source 3: John Glover, *Sufism and Jihad in Modern Senegal: The Murid Order* (Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press, 2007).
- Source 1: Ato Kwamena Onoma. The Grave Preferences of Mourides in Senegal: Migration, Belonging, and Rootedness, in: *Africa Spectrum*, 53, 3 (2018) pp. 65-88.
- Source 2: Cheikh Anta Babou, Urbanizing Mystical Islam: Making Murid Space in the Cities of Senegal in *The International Journal of African Historical Studies*, 2007, Vol. 40, No. 2 (2007) pp. 197-223.
- Source 3: Fallou Ngom, Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in *African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009) pp. 99-123.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/dictionaries-thesauruses-pictures-and-press-releases/mourides>
- Source 1 Description: "Mourides" in *The Concise Oxford Dictionary of World Religions*.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.erudit.org/fr/revues/ltp/2005-v61-n2-ltp1013/011819ar/>
- Source 1 Description: Les mourides d'Ahmadou Bamba un cas de réception de l'islam en terre négro-africaine.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/intro/islam-sufi-syncretism.htm>
- Source 1 Description: Global Security report on Sufi Syncretism.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/countries/africa/senegal>
- Source 1 Description: Action Against Hunger: Senegal.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.reuters.com/article/uk-senegal-brotherhoods/insight-would-be-presidents-court-senegals-holy-kingmakers-idUKTRE80M11420120124>
- Source 1 Description: Reuters article on the influence of Mourides on Senegalese politics.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/news/2005/03/22/model-water-provision-urban-africa>
- Source 1 Description: Water Provision in Senegal.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://seekersguidance.org/articles/poetry/kun-kaatiman-poem-by-shaykh-ahmadou-bamba/>
- Source 1 Description: Poem by Amadu Bamba.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Senegal has a history of French colonization; as such both Islamic and Roman Catholic holidays

are observed. The Mouride founder, Amadu Bamba, was once awarded the French Cross of the Legion of Merit, though he refused to wear it because of its Christian symbolism. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 47.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Mourides compete with three other Sufi brotherhoods for adherents among the Senegalese people

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The Mourides are fiercely proud of their Cheikh Amadou Bamba and are generally eager to share his story

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Amadou Bamba was strongly committed to the (nonviolent) "greater jihad," which involves moral refinement and acts of charity and justice

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: To be a committed Mouride, one must undergo initiation; however, people are de facto born into the Brotherhood.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Initiation (wird) was a major point of interest for Bamba. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 44.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: "Amadu Bamba himself discouraged the expression of class or caste differences among

his followers." Low social status is no impediment to entry into Mouride life. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 56.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Initiation (Bay'at) by a qualified teacher (cheikh) is an entry point into a deep devotion to the brotherhood.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: To become a taalibe (learner), one must become the disciple of a cleric (marabout)

Notes: Coulon 202.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, the tariqa (order) spread through attraction to the life, miracles, and teachings of Amadou Bamba. Senegal, thanks largely to the Mourides, has a reputation for religious tolerance: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xbwOJ9PFVU0>

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The previous President of Senegal, Abdoulaye Wade (2000-2012) was a Mouride. Increasingly, while the government has continued to publicly court the endorsement of the Mouride Khalifa, the brotherhood has been reticent to involve itself in political affairs.

Reference: Christian Coulon. The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal. *African Affairs*, 98(391)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Bamba declared that those who wish to learn Arabic and/or perform manual labor are to be nurtured in the group; those who desire neither are to be sent away.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4000000

Notes: Estimates are between 3 and 5 million out of Senegal's total of 14 million. Source: BBC News (<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-14344082>)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 30

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Qur'an is the central scripture for the community. Reports of the Prophet Muhammad (hadith) and Bamba's own writings also have special status.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In 610 the Angel Gabriel encountered the Prophet Muhammad at the cave of Hira' and

commanded him, "Recite!" This is commemorated annually on Laylat al-Qadr (the Night of Power).

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: See below: God revealed the Qur'an in Arabic through Jibril.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: God related the Qur'an through the Angel Jibril (Gabriel) during a 22 year period beginning in 610 CE. Tangentially related, Amadou Bamba reportedly received a revelation from Jibril in the 1890s; the location of the revelation became the city of Touba.

Reference: Christian Coulon. The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal. *African Affairs*, 98(391)

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Though not scripture properly, the writings of Amadou Bamba are held in high regard.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: From 1924 until his death in 1927 Bamba worked on the great mosque in Touba, where he had received his revelation and where he was to be entombed. Hundreds of thousands, if not millions, of pilgrims visit it each year for the Grand Magal. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 47.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious

monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: The Great Mosque in Touba is one of Africa's largest, and is part of a larger edifice that dominates the city of Touba.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 8000

Notes: The mosque is said to be the size of several football fields, 100 meters by 80 meters. See this for an Al Jazeera piece about the Grand Mosque: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nriFeEb3cVo>.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 87

Notes: "The Great Mosque has five minarets and the most famous is 286 feet (87 meters) high and known as the Lamp Fall, named after Sheikh Ibrahima Fall, one of Bamba's most influential disciples." For a virtual tour, see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=epQxczNz_44&t=6s. <https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-africa/great-mosque-touba-0011983>

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: Touba is a growing city, dominated architecturally by the Great Mosque and the Lamp Fall minaret.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– All public spaces

Notes: The image of Bamba is very common in Senegal and is thought to bring blessing (baraka) to those who venerate it (see the attached photograph).

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Imagery of Bamba typically shows his face obfuscated except for his eyes.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Icons of Bamba frequently depict him performing miracles and display angelic figures.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Angels are depicted as anthropomorphic.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Icons of Bamba include portrayals of historical figures, in this case his French captors.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Images of Bamba are believed to convey his baraka to his devotees.
<https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/intro/islam-sufi-syncretism.htm>

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit survives after the death of the body. "In death, the body remains in the ground while the soul is in the interspace or Barzakh between the two worlds. However, the two are still connected and so the bliss or punishment happens to both of them."

<https://medium.com/@xenovandestra/human-souls-journey-after-death-in-islam-54be65efe80>

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba taught that hard work in this life correlates to blessedness in the afterlife. Additionally, Mourides believe that devotion to Bamba and the cheikhs leads to a transfer of their grace (baraka) which benefits the believer after death. Fallou Ngom, Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in *African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009), 119.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Bamba taught that souls in the afterlife desire to return to earth to do more hard work and improve their eternal station, but that this is not possible. Fallou Ngom, Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in *African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009), 119.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The body is ritually washed and covered with a sheet and is to be buried within a day of death.
<https://www.memorialplanning.com/resources/religious-funerals-guide/islamic-funeral-guide>

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Mourides believe in the importance of burial in the city of Touba, near to Amadou Bamba's grave, to ensure a good afterlife. Burial or transfer of one's corpse to a plot adjacent to Bamba's is a guarantee of Paradise. Ato Kwamena Onoma. *The Grave Preferences of Mourides in Senegal: Migration, Belonging, and Rootedness*, in: *Africa Spectrum*, 53, 3 (2018) 77.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: The dahira organization provides for burial in Touba, though many Mourides prefer to be buried with their ancestors. Relocation of corpses to the Holy City is therefore theologically significant. Cheikh Anta Babou, *Urbanizing Mystical Islam: Making Murid Space in the Cities of Senegal* in *The International Journal of African Historical Studies*, 2007, Vol. 40, No. 2 (2007) 204.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The doctrine of God's oneness, tawhid, has classically been understood to preclude anthropomorphisms. The takbir ("God is greater") implies that God is beyond human limitations.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: God dwells in the Garden of Paradise (Jannah), but this is not located physically in the sky.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: An-Nar (the fire) is located in jahannam (hell), the abode of Iblis and wicked humans and jinn.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Mourides refute the accusation of shirk (associating non-God with God), though they have been accused of worshiping Bamba as Allah. Fallou Ngom, Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in African Studies Review, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009) 119.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The Caliph (head of the Mouride Order) is not seen as divine, though the first Caliph (Bamba) is imbued with supernatural properties. Mourides trust his teachings and labor in his name in large part because of the number and quality of miracles that he performed. For his part, though, Bamba wrote, "My miracles are the verses which I write." Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in African Affairs, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 198.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The Qur'an, in a refutation of normative Christianity, states, "He begets not, nor is He begotten." (Q 112:3)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: God imbues Bamba with blessing (baraka) and the cheiks with a

measure of Bamba's baraka.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Among the ninety-nine Names of God in Islam are al-Ali (the Highest) and al-Kabir (the Greatest). <https://marytn.medium.com/the-most-beautiful-names-of-god-99-names-of-allah-b898f624cada>

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God is the judge of human righteousness and fidelity.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: God has knowledge of all things; the Qur'an repeatedly stresses that God is "the knower of all" (al-'Alim).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: God is completely omniscient in normative Sunni Islam.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: One of the ninety-nine Names of God is al-Basir, the Seer of All. <https://marytn.medium.com/the-most-beautiful-names-of-god-99-names-of-allah-b898f624cada>

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an (42:11) states, "There is nothing like unto Him, and He is the Hearing, the Seeing." Scholars have classically understood this sight to be limitless.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: See above. God is omniscient in Mouridism.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Part of God's knowing a person is knowing her or his intentions (niyya). <https://blog.hautehijab.com/post/why-is-niyyah-or-intention-so-important-in-everything-we-do-including-wearing-hijab>

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Islamic scholars have generally concluded that God has knowledge of the future, though there is a tension in Islamic theology between freewill and predestination. People are responsible for their deeds even if God ordains them. Bamba had a particular affinity for the teachings of al-Ghazali. For Ghazali's thought, see Matthew Levering. Providence and Predestination in Al-Ghazali in *New Blackfriars* Vol. 92, No. 1037 (JANUARY 2011), pp. 55-70.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: There is no restriction on God's all-knowingness.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an (39:53) states, "My servants who have committed excesses against themselves, do not despair of Allah's Mercy. Surely Allah forgives all sins. He is Most Forgiving, Most Merciful."

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Many Muslims believe that God's punishment is an extension of God's infinite justice. <https://theislamicguide.com/gods-mercy-in-reward-punishment/>

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: According to the theory of occasionalism, God is the ultimate Cause of all seemingly indirect action. Ghazali, who Bamba revered, taught this position.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: God is said in the Qur'an to love (e.g. Q 2:195) those who do good.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Sunni Islam, to which the Mourides subscribe, has many examples of divine wrath. Cf. Ibn Ṭāwūs, *al-Luhūf*, 82. Divine pain is a less explored theological dimension: God's suffering would seem to challenge divine impassibility, though certain events (such as the slaying of Husayn) can be said to inflict pain of God. Cf. Muḥammad ibn 'Alī Ibn Babawayh, *'Ilal al-Sharāyī' wa-Ṣadūq* (Dar al-Mortada: Beirut, 2006), 184.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Associating anything with God (shirk) is strictly forbidden, though Mourides seem at times to join the Muslim ghulat (extremists) in considering God to be especially present in the life of a particular human, in this case, Bamba. Fallou Ngom, *Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009) 119.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: God can be said to be omnipotent as well as omniscient -- in a word, greater (akbar).

Notes: Bamba "viewed tasawwuf as a central element of Islam but only second to tawhid (science of the one-ness of God) and sharia (Islamic jurisprudence), which he considered to be the soul and body of the religion." In other words, Bamba was a monotheist even before he was a Sufi. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug.,

2003) 314.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: For this topic and its ancillaries listed below, it is significant that God not only revealed the Qur'an via Gabriel (Jabril) to Muhammad, but also that Bamba himself had a revelation at the beginning of his career as cheikh. D. Robinson, *Beyond Resistance and Collaboration: Amadu Bamba and the Murids of Senegal* in *Journal of Religion in Africa* Vol. 21, Fasc. 2 (May, 1991)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The circumstances of Bamba's vision are unclear.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Unlike some Sufi sects, Mouridism is not syncretic with indigenous beliefs and does not include the practice of divination.

<https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/intro/islam-sufi-syncretism.htm>

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The recipient of divine revelation par excellence is the Prophet Muhammad.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The power structure of Senegal is distinctive in that the Mouride marabouts (spiritual leaders) hold court in Touba where political leaders curry their favor. Monarchs and Presidents are not seen as supernaturally imbued. "The representative of the President of the Republic remains as keen as always to ask the Khalilfa to bless the government in all its actions, but the Mouride leader, for his part, has become more reserved in the support he offers to the political power." Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999,

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No
Notes: Angels and djinn have knowledge of the Hereafter.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes
Notes: Angels and djinn have knowledge of the Hereafter.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– No
Notes: In Islam, omniscience is reserved for God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: To my knowledge, Islam does not have a doctrine of angels developed enough to answer this question. Angels do have some knowledge of human affairs. <https://islamonline.net/en/angels-in-islam-creatures-of-light-2/>

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Notes: As above, the extent of angels' knowledge is a matter known only to God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: This matter is not spelled out in classical Islam, though there are examples of Gabriel (Jibril) interacting with Muhammad during emotive moments. Abdullāh Muḥammad ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī (d. 1172). *Maqṭal al-Ḥusayn*. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, 1997, 111.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Particularly Gabriel (Jibril) is entrusted with divine knowledge in order that he may relay it to Muhammad.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: I have not found Bamba writing about the will of angels.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: For Muslims, the Qur'an was revealed to Muhammad through the angel Gabriel (Jibril).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: I have not found examples of angels exhibiting positive emotion in Mouride accounts, but this is not precluded.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Though not unique to Mouridism, there are stories of Gabriel exhibiting emotion. See, for example, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn Ja'far ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, (d. 1247 or 1252). Muthīr al-Aḥzān. Beirut, Dār al-'Ulūm, 2004, 120, where angels cry out (taṣrukḥ) at the death of Muhammad's grandson Husayn.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: While not supernatural per se, Amadou Bamba is associated with a number of miracles.

Notes: Bamba's miracles are seen as proof of his authority and the basis for submission to the order's cheikhs. For Bamba's supernatural qualities, see John Glover, *Sufism and Jihad in Modern Senegal: The Murid Order* (Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press, 2007) 83 and Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 200. In the latter source Bamba is said to have transformed a seductress into a frog.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Divine omniscience extends to monitoring of believers' actions, though this is not unique to Mouridism.

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Food:

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, Bamba taught mastery over one's stomach, and winebibbing is prohibited.

Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol is forbidden in the Holy City of Touba. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 204.

Sacred object(s):

– No

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Believers are encouraged to follow in Bamba's sunnah.

Notes: "The painstaking reconstruction of Amadu Bamba's footprints in the city and enacting his activities (real or imagined) are all the more important in the contest for space, especially since Murids have long been interlopers in urban areas." Cheikh Anta Babou, *Urbanizing Mystical Islam: Making Murid Space in the Cities of Senegal* in *The*

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's position represented a rejection of his era's conception of violent jihad against colonial rule, and Muslims are forbidden from killing one another. D. Robinson, *Beyond Resistance and Collaboration: Amadu Bamba and the Murids of Senegal* in *Journal of Religion in Africa* Vol. 21, Fasc. 2 (May, 1991) 149.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Unjust killing of others is prohibited. There is space in Sunni Islam for religious tolerance. The Qur'an (2:62) says, "Whether they are the ones who believe (in the Arabian Prophet), or whether they are Jews, Christians or Sabians – all who believe in Allah and the Last Day, and do righteous deeds – their reward is surely secure with their Lord; they need have no fear, nor shall they grieve."

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's commitment to nonviolence saturates Mouride life. He replied to those demanding holy war against the French by appealing to the "holy war on souls" and the fact that jihad should only be undertaken from a position of strength. In effect, Bamba forbade the killing of French overlords. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 51.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba preached marital fidelity and refraining from sexual sin.

↳ Incest:

– I don't know

Notes: There is a lack of scholarship on this subject.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: While deception is not strictly forbidden (there is in Shi'ism a tradition of dissimilitude, taqiyya, as a means of self-preservation), immorality in general is forbidden. Bamba taught that the tongue is to be tamed in service of the heart. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 319f.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: As stated above, Bamba believed in moral integrity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: This is one of the distinctive elements of Mouridism. The Mouride motto is "Travail et Discipline" - Work and Discipline. Hard work is on level ground with religious knowledge in the Mouride value system. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-14344082>

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's example was to face risk, as is evidenced by his submission to exile and house arrest. He saw such exile as an opportunity for spiritual growth. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Filial respect and devotion to one's cheikh are important in the Mouride system. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 313.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: As stated above, a Mouride is to tame her or his tongue.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an (5:38) teaches: "As to the thief, Male or female, cut off his or her hands: a punishment by way of example, from Allah, for their crime: and Allah is Exalted in power." Interpretations of this verse have varied over the centuries; Bamba does not seem to have focused on it, though he did stress Islamic jurisprudence and God's shari'a. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 314.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Islam has a strong tradition of orthopraxy and ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Mourides observe Islamic ritual; this is especially seen in the Grand Magal pilgrimage to Touba. Christian Coulon writes, "Religious journeys, called zyara, are central to the mobilization of those who follow the way of sufi and of popular piety. The word used by the Mourides for pilgrimages of this sort is magal. This word, from the Wolof language, is derived from the verb mag which means 'to be important' or 'to be old', and magal means celebration or an anniversary." Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 196.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: For the most part, Bamba was content to leave the French power structure alone; his focus was on the spiritual purification of those who took vows of allegiance to the Mouride cheikhs. At the same time, Mourides have a reputation for proselytizing their branch of Islam. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 44. Danielle Resnick, *Urban Poverty and Populism in African Democracies* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2013)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba wrote, "Those who frequent them (the unjust rulers) because of their wealth, share in the corruption which is the source of their power." Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 313.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: The Baye Fall subsect is known for dreadlocks and colorful, though raggy, clothing.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Bamba taught the importance of soul purification.

Notes: "In face of the imposition of French authority over the people of Senegal, he shifted the battle to the control of the soul, which, for the Sufi, remains the centre that regulates people's feelings and actions. By focusing the struggle on the control of the soul, Bamba aimed to defeat two major enemies, the expansion of ceddo values, and French cultural influence, that confronted his society." Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 323.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Ultimately punishment belongs to God, though God may employ intermediaries to effect the punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: Trial (bila') is seen by many Islamic scholars as a means of spiritual refinement. Harris, Michael J. "‘But Now My Eye Has Seen You’: Yissurin Shel Ahavah as Divine Intimacy Theodicy." *The Torah U-Madda Journal*, vol. 17. New York: Rabbi Isaac Elchanan Theological Seminary, 2016-17, 76.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Trial and sadness have a purpose, though the nature of that purpose is a matter of interpretation for Islamic scholars. "[A] number of classical [Islamic] scholars composed works on it or included chapters on it in larger works. Amidst these diverse works, one notices two trends: one that sees sadness as a trial from God to be endured; and another that sees it as the mark of spiritual virtue and thus as something that guides the believer in service of the virtuous life." Paul Heck, "Sadness in Classical Islam: Its Relation to the Goals of Religion," *Emotions Across Cultures Working Papers* (New York: NYU Faculty Digital Archive, 2014) 6.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Ultimately, punishment is a recompense for wickedness. Conversely, fidelity and righteousness are rewarded with a happy afterlife. Hard work, too, is to be rewarded. Devotees worked hard for Bamba, in exchange for "assurance of paradise after death." Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 41.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba emphasized the reward for the righteous more than he did the punishment for the wicked. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 42.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: According to Islamic scholars, the pain of hellfire is ineffable but severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– No

Notes: Discipline and refinement are important for Bamba, but there is no sense that God punishes believers in this lifetime for their sins.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

Notes: God rewards especially those who work hard in the service of Islam. Similarly, there is eternal bliss for those who submit to Bamba's teaching. He said, "Whosoever he may be, he who becomes my disciple shall be saved in this world and the next. Any mouride who seeks refuge with me shall go to paradise and shall not know the burning embers of hell." Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 51.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Notes: For Bamba, divine blessing is a reward, not an incentive.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For Bamba, the purpose of life is striving to attain reward in the afterlife; he emphasized this point often.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Bamba does not seem to dwell on the nature of eternal happiness and does suggest that reward can be temporal as well as eternal.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Fallou Ngom notes that, "The Murids' determined pursuit of 'paradise in this life and in the afterlife' (through hard work and faith in Bamba's teachings and his baraka) has often subjected them to criticism of arrogance." Fallou Ngom, *Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009) 119.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

Notes: Hardship may be a sign of righteousness, as evidenced by Bamba enduring decades of exile (in Gabon and Mauritania) and house arrest in Senegal.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Economic power is seen as a divine reward. "There is a strong belief that material success is generated through baraka by one's marabout, who are believed to reflect God's will. When material success occurs, it is widely interpreted as a result of following God's will and enjoying God's favor rather than individual genius." Mark Titus Hoover, *The Mourides of Senegal: A Gospel of Work, Solidarity & God*

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Notes: Unlike many of his coreligionists, Bamba did not preach violent jihad against the French. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 321.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: The mainly agrarian Mourides found that the virtue of hard work let to economic prosperity. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival

of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 202.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's exiles only served to bring attention to his movement and attract new converts, so in this way his "journey" was successful as a result of his fidelity.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Reproductive success might not have been a reward for Bamba, but it was visited on him. His sons (and now grandson) have served as caliphs since his death.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's relatives, especially his brothers, were recipients of good fortune as a result of his hard work. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 44.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Bamba was seen as a the boroom jamono, or "master of the age," though he was not a messianic figure per se.' John Glover, *Sufism and Jihad in Modern Senegal: The Murid Order* (Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press, 2007) 83.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Giving financially to the group and community associations are important for group solidarity. "In Touba, social services are free and marabouts disperse their addiya freely so as to demonstrate this sense of sharing publicly. Without the strong sense of safety and trust inspired by Wolof culture and reinforced by Mouride spirituality, Mouride adherents would not have access to the capital and networks needed for their economic success." Mark Titus Hoover, *The Mourides of Senegal: A Gospel of Work, Solidarity & God*, 35.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: The virtue of hard work is a conventional norm for Mourides, whereas obedience to shari'a is a matter of Islamic morality.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: God rewards those who work hard in the service of Bamba's mission. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 312.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of

anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba preached the norm of hard work, writing, "What those who passed away want the most is to have the opportunity to come back to this world for any short duration so that they may perform some additional work that would benefit them when they return." Whether Bamba is a mere human or an "anthropomorphic being" is a matter of interpretation, as veneration of him verges on adoration. Fallou Ngom, *Aḥmadu Bamba's Pedagogy and the Development of 'Ajamī Literature in African Studies Review*, Apr 2009, Vol. 52, No. 1 (Apr., 2009) 106.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: Bamba's egalitarianism made no distinction for class or station, so norms are universal for the Mourides. Mark Titus Hoover, *The Mourides of Senegal: A Gospel of Work, Solidarity & God*, 35.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: There is no ascetic requirement for celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Amadou Bamba recommended celibacy outside of marriage and refraining from "unlawful sexual pleasure." Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 320.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Bamba's focus on sexual ethics was aimed at males.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Islamic law is enforced in Senegal; this extends to the practice of adultery.
<https://sunulex.africa/en/the-senegalese-legal-system/>

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Likewise, Islamic sexual norms are applied to females.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: As Sufi Sunnis, Mourides are expected to observe traditional Islamic fasts, including during the month of Ramadan.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "Amadu Bamba identified seven organs through which the lower self works and described the method to counter its deleterious effect on the heart and mind of people. These organs are: the stomach, the tongue, the genitalia, the feet, the eyes, the hands and the ears." With the stomach, "Bamba warns against consuming illicitly acquired food and eating too much." Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 320.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: While not mandatory, it is common for Mourides to lavish gifts on the Cheikhs and to give to the poor. This can be traced back to the group's origins. Bamba's post-exilic popularity threatened the social structure, as parents were losing sons to Bamba's service and merchants' clients were spending their money on the marabouts; in response, the French exiled him again, this time to Mauritania.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Prayer, study, and hard work are all demanding on a Mouride's time. The Grammy-winning Mouride Youssou N'Dour says, "Mouridism is for me two paths - one is the way to God, the other path is the doctrine of work and dignity. Because if you don't work, you hold your hand out and lose your dignity." <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-14344082>

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The primary ethical principle that Mourides adopt is hard work. Because of this, many early converts came from lower classes in which agrarian life demanded a strong work ethic. Bamba was egalitarian with regard to race, writing, "The man most esteemed by Allah is he who fears him the most, without discrimination of any kind... Skin color has nothing to do with a man's foolishness or of his poor understanding." Saliou Mbacke, "The Mouride Order" in *World Faiths Development Dialogue*, sponsored by the Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Affairs, Georgetown University, Washington, DC, 2016, 7.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Mourides constitute just one of several Sufi brotherhoods in Senegal; there is considerable cooperation and mutual respect between them. P. Marty notes that Bamba himself had an affinity for the Tijāni and Qādiri tariqas. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 4

Notes: Daily Sunni prayers are required by Islam. Additionally, initiation rituals are stressed. Despite attracting a significant early following, Bamba continued as a disciple of the Mauritanian marabout Shaikh Sidiya Baba, who consecrated Bamba as a muqaddam (someone who administers the initiation oath) who could initiate Qādiriyya. Today, initiation through a Cheikh is important for Mourides. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 42.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 2000000

Notes: The grand magal brings together hundreds of thousands of devotees each year, or even as many as one to two million according to some observers. Touba and the tomb of the Cheikh are thus the symbolic centre of the brotherhood. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 195.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Grand Magal pilgrimage to Touba takes place annually on the anniversary of Bamba's exile to Gabon, the 18th of the month of Safar. As many as a few million devotees make this pilgrimage. Dang, Christine Thu Nhi (June 3, 2013). "Pilgrimage Through Poetry: Sung Journeys Within the Murid Spiritual Diaspora". *Islamic Africa*. 4 (1): 69-101.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: I have not found documentation on orthodoxy checks, though presumably a devotee's cheikh ensures right belief. "Amadu Bamba distinguished between three major types of

teachers: the shaikh of instruction, responsible for classical teaching of the Qur'an and the Islamic religious sciences (law, mysticism, tradition of the Prophet Muhammad, interpretation of the Qur'an and worship); the shaikh of education whose aim is to educate the soul and guide the disciple towards spiritual perfection; and the shaikh of tarqiyya or ascension." Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa* , Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa (Aug., 2003) 317f.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: As with orthodoxy, orthopraxy seems to be the dominion of a Mouride's cheikh. In particular, the cheikh of education teaches Islamic practice to devotees.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Synchronic practices such as pilgrimage, prayer, and the visitation of Bamba's tomb are important for the Mourides. All-night prayer and singing sessions called daa'ira are conducted during the Grand Magal. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs* , Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 198.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: "Amadu Bamba identified seven organs through which the lower self works and described the method to counter its deleterious effect on the heart and mind of people. These organs are: the stomach, the tongue, the genitalia, the feet, the eyes, the hands and the ears." Intoxicants, forbidden in Islam, would seem to inhibit proper use of the mind and heart. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa* , Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa (Aug 2003) 319f.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to abstaining from alcohol, Mourides are expected to be moderately ascetic in their food consumption. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug 2003) 320.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: In the Baye Fall subgroup, members adorn dreadlocks with colorful beads. See <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C2r6ZIS4wiM> for examples.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the above-mentioned hairstyle, the Baye Fall wear colorful garments during the Grand Magal. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C2r6ZIS4wiM>

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Arabic proficiency was important for Bamba. In 1903 he divided his followers into four categories: (1) those who desire to learn Arabic, (2) those who desire to work without learning, (3) those who desire both, and (4) those who desire neither, who are to be driven out to "go where he wills." Arabic knowledge thus enjoys equal status with hard work among Mouride values. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 52.

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Male members are referred to a "brothers."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Mourides are predominantly located in Senegal

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Groups like Action Against Hunger provide food for malnourished Senegalese, who make up roughly 9% of the population. <https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/countries/africa/senegal>

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Mourides living abroad, especially in Europe, raise money to send back to the poor in Senegal. This fundraising, achieved through vending goods on the streets, is highly organized and reflects Bamba's propensity to share donations with the poor. <https://www.theperspective.se/religion-and-business-the-mourides-of-senegal/>

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Senegal scores very low on human development indexes. According to the IMF, "numerous family and religious festivals...weigh upon the country's productivity and growth;" these include the Grand Magal to Touba. International institutions provide poverty relief. International Monetary Fund, "Senegal: Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper" (2013)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: "What distinguishes Touba from other urban centres is that religious leaders can deploy the religious devotion of Mouride disciples to mobilize vast sums of money and labour for major urban projects." These projects include the building of hospitals. Ellen E. Foley and Cheikh Anta Babou, "Diaspora, Faith, and Science: Building a Mouride Hospital in Senegal" in *African Affairs*, 110/438, 75

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: While much room remains for improvement, social services in Senegal have increased greatly in recent years according to UNICEF. <https://www.unicef.org/senegal/en/equity-governance-and-social-policy>

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's stress on religious education cannot be understated. He taught, "that the Prophet had instructed him to educate the students who are attached to him to purify their souls and secure spiritual fulfillment." Bamba taught that a devotee should have three teachers: a cheikh of instruction, a cheikh of education, and a cheikh of "tarqiyya or ascension." These cheikhs help the Mouride to refine her or his soul and character. "The Cheikh's educational method also involved putting the Mouride disciple in an isolated place called a daara, where he was trained in Islamic teachings and where he was safe from any bad influences in the society. The talibé (disciple) remains in the daara until the end of his spiritual training, then is ready to return to society (villages, cities), immune to its vices and bad influences." The daaras included teachers of the Qur'an and of religious sciences. Saliou Mbacke, "The Mouride Order" in *World Faiths Development Dialogue*, sponsored by the Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Affairs, Georgetown University, Washington, DC, 2016, 3, 5. Cheikh Anta Babou, "Educating the Murid: Theory and Practices of Education in Amadu Bamba's Thought" in *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Aug., 2003, Vol. 33, Fasc. 3, *Islamic Thought in 20th-Century Africa* (Aug., 2003) 317f.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Senegalese government provides for the education of children. In Touba, many services are provided by the Brotherhood, which is powerful enough as to render the Holy City as a de facto independent city-state. The two merged during the Presidency of Abdoulaye Wade, a Mouride. On the whole, Human Rights Tracker gives Senegal a score of 58.1% on the right to education. <https://www.unicef.org/senegal/en/equity-governance-and-social-policy>. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 207. Danielle Resnick, *Urban Poverty and Populism in African Democracies* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2013). <https://rightstracker.org/en/country/SEN>

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: While the Caliph is the central temporal authority figure for all Mourides, local cheikhs are in effect more influential for individual believers. Still, Mouridism has a formalized hierarchical structure and is well organized. Saliou Mbacke, "The Mouride Order" in *World Faiths Development Dialogue*, sponsored by the Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Affairs, Georgetown University, Washington, DC, 2016, 10.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: During the Grand Magal, political elites secure audiences in which they seek the blessing of Mouride marabouts. The connection between the ruling class and the Mouride hierarchy dates back to the time of Bamba, whose reciprocal relationship with the French authority figures secured his release from exile. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 202.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: While there are no hotels in Touba, residents supply lodging and sustenance to pilgrims during the Grand Magal. The Baye Fall subgroup oversees much of the organization for the pilgrimage. <https://www.reuters.com/article/uk-senegal-pilgrimage/million-muslim-pilgrims-flock-to-senegals-mecca-idUKL0867640420070308>

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, a number of NGOs operate in Senegal to address poverty and hunger.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Touba's Hygiene Brigade oversees some aspects of public health concerning water. In Touba land and water are provided for free, following Bamba's wishes. Felicity Thompson, "Water woes in Senegal's holy city" *World Health Organization. Bulletin of the World Health Organization*; Geneva Vol. 88, Iss. 1, (Jan 2010) 7.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The organization Senegalaise des Eaux manages the water supply for the Senegalese government. The World Bank declared that, "the Senegal case is regarded as a model of public-private partnership in sub-Saharan Africa." <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/news/2005/03/22/model-water-provision-urban-africa>

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: "Among other patronage promises, [President] Wade oversaw the construction of a new road from Touba to Mbacké, which is where the leader of the Mouridiyya, Cheikh Saliou Mbacké, resides...He also promised to build an airport there to facilitate religious pilgrimages." This reflects a partnership between the government and the religious hierarchy with regards to transportation issues. Danielle Resnick, *Urban Poverty and Populism in African Democracies* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2013)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Senegalese government oversees the country's transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: As Sunni Muslims, Mourides pay zakat, though the majority of their giving is beyond the requirements of Islamic tithing. This form of donation, called adya, is given to one's cheikh. Donal Cruise O'Brien, "Le talibé mouride : La soumission dans une confrérie religieuse sénégalaise" *Cahiers d'Études africaines* 1970, 572. adakar.com, "Le 'Adya': La force financière de la communauté mouride" (2019): <http://news.adakar.com/h/112873.html>

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Senegalese imposes a personal income tax of up to 40% on individuals. <https://taxsummaries.pwc.com/senegal/individual/taxes-on-personal-income>

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The Baye Fall, named for Bamba's disciple Ibrahima Fall, are custodians of Touba during the Grand Magal (meaning "important" or "old" in Wolof). They wear colorful rags and dreadlocks and both solicit alms and provide security (they carry clubs for rule enforcement) vis-à-vis the pilgrims. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Especially outside of Touba, Senegalese are subject to the local police. The Naval Postgraduate School states, "Senegal has a stable democracy and police forces that were established prior to Senegalese independence in 1960, but it is still uncertain if they can become a police force that contributes to national and personal security capable of dealing with human and narcotic trafficking, transnational crimes, and international terrorism." <https://calhoun.nps.edu/handle/10945/50607>

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba's great-grandson, Saliou Mbacke, says, "There are sharia judges. It is usually the imam who plays that role. The khalifa can cancel any judgment because he puts the imams there. The imam is tasked to read the law. Touba is distinct. In the jurisdiction of Touba, the khalifa has the ultimate word on everything." <https://berkeleycenter.georgetown.edu/interviews/a-discussion-with-sheikh-saliou-mbacke-continental-coordinator-of-ifapa>

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Touba is largely autonomous from the bureaucratic structures of Senegal. The Mourides have a strong notion of the separation between religious and political authority, though one of their own (Abdoulaye Wade) was president from 2000-2012. Ellen E. Foley and Cheikh Anta Babou, "Diaspora, Faith, and Science: Building a Mouride Hospital in Senegal" in African Affairs, 110/438, 84. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in African Affairs , Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 203.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear what jurisdiction the shari'a courts have for punishing wrongdoers, but they presumably have authority in civil matters.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Under the leadership of President Wade, a Mouride, Senegal abolished the death penalty in 2004 (becoming the fourth West African country to do so). Amnesty International, "West Africa: Senegal abolishes the death penalty, who's next?" (2004)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba was exiled to Gabon (seven years) and Mauritania (five) when the French felt threatened by his rapid popularity and accompanying level of societal influence. The charges were vague, as the French could not accuse Bamba of preaching a holy war of resistance to the colonial oppressors. Christian Coulon, "The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal" in *African Affairs*, Apr., 1999, Vol. 98, No. 391 (Apr., 1999) 198.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably the State has authority over property disputes.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Bamba, "viewed tasawwuf [Sufism] as a central element of Islam but only second to tawhid (science of the oneness of God) and sharia (Islamic jurisprudence), which he considered to be the soul and body of the religion." Shari'a courts

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: According to Sunulex.africa, "Both French civil law and Muslim law apply" in Senegalese society. <https://sunulex.africa/en/the-senegalese-legal-system/>

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The group, following Bamba, is staunchly pacifist. It officially condemned the 9/11 attacks as un-Islamic and has denounced al-Qaeda. Following Islamic tradition, Bamba distinguished the "greater jihad" as "holy war against the vices of greed, falsehood, slander, pride, and all that can harm either oneself or others." <https://www.reuters.com/article/uk-senegal-brotherhoods/insight-would-be-presidents-court-senegals-holy-kingmakers-idUKTRE80M11420120124> Saliou Mbacke, "The Mouride Order" in *World Faiths Development Dialogue*, sponsored by the Berkley Center for Religion, Peace & World Affairs, Georgetown University, Washington, DC, 2016, 4.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Though Bamba taught nonviolent jihad of the soul, he did encourage his devotees early on to serve the colonial state. The French hoped that good relations with the Mourides would lead to military recruitment, which indeed panned out during WWI: they granted Bamba the Cross of the Legion of Honor (though he refused to wear it because of its Christian imagery).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Forces armées du Sénégal (Senegalese armed forces) provide for the common defense of all. Notably, though, Senegal has avoided the civil warfare and other violent conflicts that have plagued many West African countries since decolonization. Since colonial times there has been a recognition that just as the government has political power, so the marabouts have religious power, and the Mouride establishment has been credited with the continued success of Senegal's peaceful democracy.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Wolof, the Senegalese lingua franca, is the primary language of communication among the Mourides, though Bamba stressed the importance of learning Arabic for religious reasons. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971) 52.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: French and Wolof language education is provided to the public, while more than half of Mourides also attend at least a few years of Qur'anic school in which Arabic is taught. Pierre André and Jean-Luc Demonsant, "Koranic Schools in Senegal: A real barrier to formal education?" (2009), 1.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic hijri calendar is used for religious purposes. One of the holiest days of the Mouride year is the 18th of Safar, when devotees commemorate Bamba's exile by the French during the Grand Magal pilgrimage.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Gregorian calendar is used in Senegalese commercial life. Christian and Islamic holidays are celebrated, with the latter determined by the hijri calendar.
<https://www.officeholidays.com/countries/senegal/2021>

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Groundnut production is integral to Senegalese society, and Mourides are estimated to produce roughly half of the country's groundnut crop. Bamba stressed and celebrated the hard work of agrarian life, and the economic autonomy that this allowed the Mourides contributed to their high station in the political power structure. Donald B. Cruise O'Brien, *The Mourides of Senegal: the political and economic organization of an Islamic brotherhood* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group

in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: NGOs like Action Against Hunger provide food relief for impoverished Senegalese.
<https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/countries/africa/senegal>

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Christian Coulon. The Grand Magal in Touba: A Religious Festival of the Mouride Brotherhood of Senegal. *African Affairs*, 98(391)

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